

The Interplay Between Cognitive Flexibility, Emotion Regulation, and Work-Life Balance: Exploring the Mediating Effect of Job Crafting

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Abstract

With the rise of remote work practices, employees' personal and professional lives have become more intertwined, highlighting the significance of the work-life balance issue. Within academic research, there is a growing interest in exploring the coping mechanisms used by employees to uphold a harmonious work-life balance. This study focuses on emotion regulation (reappraisal and suppression) and cognitive flexibility (alternatives and control) as strategies utilized by employees to preserve their work-life balance and the mediating effect of job crafting in this relationship. To reveal the mentioned relationships, structural equation modeling is employed. The participants were chosen among workers whose organizations implemented a remote work policy due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Findings show both dimensions of cognitive flexibility and the reappraisal dimension of emotion regulation have important effects on job crafting. It is also demonstrated that job crafting significantly affects work-life balance, but the mediation effect cannot be proved with this structural equation model.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Cognitive Flexibility, Emotion Regulation, Job Crafting, COVID-19, Remote Work

JEL Code: I31, J20, J81, M12

1. Introduction

According to Glass & Estes (1997), occupational choices have an impact on the place of living, non-work activities, children's schools, activities of children, and spouses/partners. In contrast, a person's work life might be influenced secondarily because of their preferences for their non-work life (Netemeyer et al., 2004). ...”.

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When considered in the context of organizational psychology, it was easier to draw the boundary between work and non-work life in organization development assessments before COVID-19. Because the employee would come to the workplace in the morning, complete his/her working hours, and start his/her non-work life activities. It was possible for non-work thoughts to be reflected in the workplace, but the boundary violation of work and non-work life was generally cognitive. It had become common to carry out psychological studies to ensure that the employee was minimally affected by cognitive negativities and to ensure that employees received psychological support when necessary.

Despite all the negative situations and limited opportunities, it is thought that individuals with high cognitive flexibility and who can use emotion regulation strategies will also have high job crafting skills (Lichtenthaler & Fischbach, 2018: 14; Kim et al., 2018). In this way, thanks to job crafting, it was thought that time could be gained to provide work-life balance by executing the work in a practical way in cognitive, task, and relational dimensions (Sturges, 2012; Yepes-Baldo et al., 2018). This study, it is aimed to see how individuals who can achieve work-life balance advocate their emotional regulation and cognitive flexibility processes. Also, how job crafting is shaped cognitively and emotionally. With COVID-19, organizations want to continue to use the advantages of teleworking after the lockdowns. For this reason, the physical limits of work-life balance should be examined more in the future. It is the first time that these four variables have been studied together and made a unique contribution. In this way, it offers a unique perspective and contribution to the literature. While environmental effects are at the forefront in work-life balance studies related to human psychology, individual cognitive and emotional processes are at the forefront in this study. The present study will be an original resource for those who want to work with these variables again.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Work-Life Balance

With the COVID-19 pandemic, the balance between work and life has been affected by the move of work life to home. Individuals have had to integrate more work activities into their private living spaces. So having flexibility, sociability, and individuality in work and non-work activities (Barnett, 1999) is more important nowadays. Work-life balance is the term to describe an individual's ability to control when, where, and how they work (Allen, 2001). Work-life balance is all activities both at work and at home with minimal role conflict and includes satisfaction (Clark, 2001: 348). According to Lockwood (2003), work-life balance is the demand balance in the individual's work and private life. Work-life balance is also defined as the individual's preoccupation with his roles in his work and private life at the same level, and getting satisfaction from these roles (Greenhaus et al., 2003). The concept of work-life balance examines the balance or conflicts in work and life domains (Maxwell & McDougall, 2004).

Wayne et al. (2020), highlight that work and life resources (for example, enriched work and life characteristics, work, and family support) are positively associated with balance satisfaction. In general, work resource is more related to

balance satisfaction compared to personal and family resources. In terms of processes, work resources are related to less work-to-life imbalance and more work-to-life enrichment, resulting in greater balance. In contrast, aspects of life to work imbalance and enrichment are weakly associated with balance.

In the present study, work-life balance is defined as the regulation of work-to-life imbalance that arises due to work-related tension, time confusion, and work demands, and the regulation of life-to-work imbalance created by non-work demands and tension by using cognitive and emotional strategies.

2.2. Cognitive Flexibility

Cognitive flexibility is an effective ability to evaluate the situation in challenging processes and to produce new solutions. It is known that thoughts about events affect emotions and bodily physiological responses. The individual's capacity to change cognitions, that is, his/her thoughts, is important to avoid bodily physiological symptoms that stress the individual about an event and to have feelings that the individual does not complain about instead of the feelings that make the individual feel uncomfortable. Cognitive flexibility refers to individuals selectively preparing their conceptual systems to change against environmental stimuli (Scott, 1962). Cognitive flexibility was defined by Spiro and Jehng (1990: 169) as “the ability to adaptively re-assemble diverse elements of knowledge to fit the particular needs of a given understanding or problem-solving situation”. Cognitive flexibility is the ability of an individual to change their cognitive sets, perspectives, thoughts, thinking styles or thinking strategies (Diamond, 2013; Miyake et al., 2000). In conclusion, cognitive flexibility is a specific way of assessing competence in modifying cognitive clusters, which differs across various measures. When faced with a stressful situation, cognitively flexible individuals can cope with the stressful event more easily because they can handle situations effectively and positively (Dennis & Vander Wal, 2010). Cognitive flexibility is handled as two dimensions: alternatives and control.

Self-efficacy while being flexible, motivation to adapt to events, and awareness of alternatives in communication are factors that increase individuals' cognitive flexibility. Cognitive flexibility should not be limited to communication, individuals should also be aware of alternatives to cope with all life events and difficult situations (Dennis & Vander Wal, 2010). In this way, generating alternative solutions can spread to all areas of life.

According to Anderson and Martin (1995), individuals with high cognitive flexibility are also aware of alternatives, and this is related to self-efficacy, awareness, and willingness. While the individual's search for alternatives is an indicator of his willingness, his self-efficacy will be strengthened when he adapts to complex situations. The search for alternatives can also occur with one's thinking about the self, and the sense of curiosity is one of the important factors that triggers this desire for research (Savickas & Porfeli, 2012). Accepting illogical ideas directly without considering alternative ideas is due to reasoning biases caused by abnormal and negatively perceived events, leading the individual to collect limited data (Van der Gaag, 2006).

One of the beneficial aspects of creating *alternatives* is that the individual can develop an attitude towards problem-solving in stressful life events, but this is different from problem-solving skills (Schur, 1999). Using alternatives as a strategy also provides coping flexibility, and it covers an adaptive and evaluable process (Kato, 2012). In the cognitive-behavioral approach, one must be able to see positive alternatives while thinking about events in order to stop cognitive distortions. Individuals who can achieve this process will also be able to feel the emotion they desire. In the absence of alternatives that can be produced through cognitive flexibility, rigidity-related depressive symptoms may occur. Individuals who do not have flexibility, that is, individuals with cognitive rigidity, may have an all-or-nothing way of thinking (Young et al., 2001).

When *control* is compared with the alternatives, it had a positive effect like the alternatives, and was observed that the level of cognitive flexibility and the tendency to use seeking social support, which is a coping strategy, increased. Instead of destructive cognitive strategies such as self-blame or wishful thinking, individuals can be motivated by more constructive cognitive strategies (e.g., problem-solving) by perceiving situations as controllable as a type of cognitive flexibility. In addition, using social support is an effective and constructive strategy that can be used when faced with difficult situations (Dennis & Vander Wal, 2010). Thanks to control, individuals can shape events around them, and individuals can cope with the next step using their effort and self-discipline (Savickas & Porfeli, 2012).

2.3. Emotion Regulation

Emotion regulation is defined as the emergence, regulation, and maintenance of emotions in terms of the intensity of feeling and the way emotions are expressed through internal and external processes (Thompson, 1994). Thompson and Calkins (1996) stated that being aware of emotions and understanding emotions are effective in emotion regulation, but it is not necessary to control emotions directly, and in fact, all emotions are functional. Emotion regulation helps people overcome unwanted emotion, and this method can be considered as a coping strategy (Leahy et al., 2011). In this study, the dimensions of Gross and John (2003) were used. Reappraisal and suppression are explained.

According to Gross and John (2003), *reappraisal* is an antecedent-focused strategy, that is, it occurs before the emotion and intervenes before the emotion reactions are fully formed, and this indicates that the reappraisal can change the emotions that the individual will experience later on as desired. More specifically, reappraisal decreases the experiential and behavioral components of unwanted emotion, and reappraisal is more commonly used to reduce negative emotion (Gross & John, 2003). It was stated that reappraisal is a good method in crisis situations (Xu et al., 2020).

According to Gross and John (2003), *suppression* is a response-focused strategy, that is, it comes later than emotion when looking at emotional responses, thus changing the behavioral aspect of emotional responses. Suppression inhibits behaviors that result from emotional responses (Goldin et al., 2008). Suppression, by its nature, is applied after the emotion, reduces the expressed behaviors, and increases the

sympathetic action of the cardiovascular system (Gross, 2002). When used frequently, suppression causes deterioration in interpersonal communication, weakening of memory, decreased psychological well-being, increased depressive symptoms, and decreased emotional control in the long term (Dennis, 2007).

2.4. Job Crafting

Being able to revise the work or shape the work of the individual in line with his abilities can save the time people spend on work. With the COVID-19 pandemic, the process of working from home has shown that work can interfere more with life. For this reason, shaping the work and providing practical solutions in line with the individual's abilities will enable him to devote more time to his private life. It can be said that employees who can achieve this through both cognitive and emotional processes can contribute to work-life balance. The idea that employees should be able to make their own decisions to shape their jobs has been debated since Katz and Kahn's (1966: 124) concept of role innovation. Staw and Boettger's (1990) sculpting activities, and task revision concepts were the first to pave the way for job crafting. Job crafting was first defined as "the physical and cognitive changes individuals make in the task or relational boundaries of their work" (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). In this study, three dimensions defined by Wrzesniewski and Dutton (2001) were used: Task crafting, relational crafting, and cognitive crafting.

Task crafting is a form of job crafting that focuses on changing the task boundaries of job tasks (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). Task crafting involves employees adding or subtracting from tasks, and employees customizing tasks by varying the time, energy, and attention devoted to each task based on their skills. (Ghitulescu, 2006). Employees can offer new ways to improve their work, minimize unpleasant tasks, or add preferred tasks (Leana et al., 2009).

Cognitive crafting is a psychological factor that includes reading clues about the cognitive and intellectual aspects of the job (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). Cognitive crafting is called changing the perceptions of employees about tasks in the workplace and relationships with colleagues based on uncertainties and uncertainties in their job roles (Ghitulescu, 2006). Cognitive crafting is also about an employee's efforts to construe and perceive his job (Wrzesniewski et al., 2013).

Relational crafting is a dimension in which the relational boundaries of the work are changed by the employees (Wrzesniewski & Dutton, 2001). Relational crafting is the change of interaction between people, also determined by task discretion and task complexity (Ghitulescu, 2006). Crafting relations with other individual, helps workers have more supportive and rewarding interactions, and relational developments result in the emergence of belonging (Vogel et al., 2016). Considering work life, as an example, hotel employees have a variety of interpersonal relationships, not only with clients but also with colleagues and supervisors (Ma & Qu, 2011). This shows that relational crafting also has different aspects.

3. The Present Study

In daily life and work, people encounter various events, each evoking distinct emotion. Those who embrace flexible thinking and reappraisal can effectively manage discomfort, shaping their desired emotions and overcoming challenges. This skill fosters adaptability, enhancing both problem-solving and emotional control, allowing individuals to approach situations from different angles and choose the most suitable emotional response. At the same time, the situation is associated with alternatives (e.g. Siemer, Yoon, & Joormann, 2010; Malooly et al., 2013), and being cognitively flexible allows an individual to think differently about an event. Thanks to the cognitive flexibility, the individual is not content with just one thought in the event. Being aware that there may be different alternatives in the event, the individuals choose the most appropriate thought for themselves. Thanks to reappraisal, control, and alternatives, it is possible to design or even craft work (e.g. Lichtenthaler & Fischbach, 2018; Kim et al., 2018). Because task crafting, cognitive crafting, and relational crafting can act in the same direction with the outputs of reappraisal and cognitive flexibility. Individuals benefit from cognitive processes while crafting tasks. In addition, different alternatives related to the job are seen, and the task is crafted appropriately. On the other hand, cognitive crafting requires a great deal of cognitive flexibility. Using cognitive flexibility has similarities with crafting individuals' cognition. When individuals want to craft negative communication in relationships, they still use alternatives. For example, when the colleague does not greet, and the thought is based on the fact that the colleague is tired and busy, alternative thoughts come into play and contribute to relational crafting.

H1a: People, who have higher scores on alternatives, would be more likely to have higher levels of job crafting's all dimensions.

H1b: People, who have higher scores on control, would be more likely to have higher levels of job crafting's all dimensions.

H1c: People, who have higher scores on reappraisal, would be more likely to have higher levels of job crafting's all dimensions.

Some individuals may not be flexible and evaluative in the face of events. Although the event may make the individual feel uncomfortable at first, they can either accept or suppress the emotions they are uncomfortable with thanks to the suppression of feelings. Therefore, the individual may experience the effects of problems in daily and work life for a little longer. In addition, it is not very usual for individuals to do their work in a more practical way even if they do not have a problem. Because suppression refers to suppressing the emotion instead of handling an event from different aspects and changing the emotions experienced as a result. Due to suppression, individuals deal with the event only in one dimension and are far from the capacity to change their emotions. Individuals do not choose between emotions without being aware of other aspects of the event, and they are content to cover up the emotions they feel. Due to suppression, it becomes difficult to design or even craft the work. Because task crafting, cognitive crafting, and relational crafting move in the opposite direction with the outputs of suppression. Individuals benefit from cognitive processes while crafting their tasks. For example, when the colleague does not greet, the feeling is based on the co-worker's dislike of the individual, and if positive alternatives are not sought, suppression feelings inhibit relational crafting.

H2: People, who have higher scores on suppression, would be more likely to have lower levels of job crafting's all dimensions.

The positive effects of task, cognitive, and relational dimensions of job crafting provide benefits for work life. Because employees who have a say over their duties and work relations can be more productive at work. Motivation and productivity are kept high by practicing the work with cognitive crafting skills. Job crafting has an important function not only in work life but also in private life. Employees manage their work better, reflecting fewer problems in their private lives. Additionally, with the COVID-19 pandemic, the rate of working from home has increased. Work and life have been moved to the same environment. People's homes have been both workplaces and living spaces. Therefore, job crafting has an important role in maintaining the work-life balance. Employees who can craft tasks and have cognitive crafting skills can devote more time to their private lives. In addition, thanks to relational craft, individuals can communicate more easily with their distant colleagues and can spend more time in private life by completing the work faster. When the task, cognitive, and relational dimensions of job crafting are not activated, negative consequences for work-life may occur, or for positive results, regardless of the employee, the job should be designed by the organization in accordance with the employee's character. Because the employee, who does not have a say over the tasks and work-related relations, may need a job description by the organization in accordance with the abilities and characteristics of the employee to be more productive at work. Otherwise, the employee who develops a point of view with suppression mechanisms does not make an additional effort to be productive. Employees who do not use their cognitive crafting skills cannot practice their work and may lose their motivation and efficiency. Job crafting has an important function not only in work life but also in private life. Therefore, when the work is not better managed by the employee, more problems may be reflected in private life. Additionally, with the COVID-19 pandemic, the rate of working from home has increased. Work and life have been moved to the same environment. People's homes have been both workplaces and living spaces. Therefore, job crafting is effective in providing work-life balance. Not crafting tasks and not using cognitive crafting may result in less time for private life. In addition, when the relational craft is not used, it is more difficult to communicate with a distant colleague and the work is completed more slowly, leaving less time for private life.

H3a: People, who have higher scores on task crafting, would be more likely to have higher levels of work-life balance's all dimensions.

H3b: People, who have higher scores on cognitive crafting, would be more likely to have higher levels of work-life balance's all dimensions.

H3c: People, who have higher scores on relational crafting, would be more likely to have higher levels of work-life balance's all dimensions.

H4a: Job crafting has a mediating effect in the relationship between cognitive flexibility and work-life balance.

H4b: Job crafting has a mediating effect in the relationship between emotion regulation and work-life balance.

4. Methodology, Data Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

Sample

Participants were selected from individuals whose institutions have switched to a work-from-home system due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The sampling method of the study is convenience sampling due to COVID-19. Participants were reached via LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, and Whatsapp, and approximately 1500 people were contacted and invited to participate in the study. In this study, 310 people participated, but since 3 of the participants did not work from home, 3 data were excluded from the study. Thus, the data collected from a total of 307 participants were analyzed. The study consisted of 300 participants from different cities of Turkey, and 7 participants whose native language is Turkish and living outside Turkey. Of these participants, 190 (61.9%) were aged between 18 and 29, 89 (29%) were aged between 30 and 41, 24 (7.8%) were aged between 42 and 53, 3 (1%) were aged between 54 and 65, and 1 (0.3%) were aged 66 years and over.

The majority of the participants (61.9%) are between the ages of 18-29, 30% have an income level between 3001 TL and 6000 TL, and 20.5% have an income level of more than 15000 TL. While 50.8% of the participants are at university level, 47.9% are Masters / Ph.D. level. More details are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Participants

Variables	<i>N</i>	%
Age		
18-29	190	61.9
30-41	89	29
42-53	24	7.8
54-65	3	1
65+	1	0.3
Gender		
Female	177	57.7
Male	129	42
Prefer not to answer	1	0.3
Education		
Primary School	0	0
Secondary School	0	0
High School	4	1.3
University	156	50.8
Master / Ph.D.	147	47.9
Working years in profession		
1-3 years	149	48.5
4-6 years	67	21.8
7-9 years	28	9.1
10-12 years	22	7.2
More than 12 years	41	13.4
Household Income		
0-3000 TL	11	3.6
3001-6000 TL	92	30
6001-9000 TL	57	18.6
9001-12000 TL	50	16.3
12001-15000 TL	34	11.1

15001 TL and above	63	20.5
Officially work from home before the COVID-19		
There was no working from home.	243	79.2
1-3 Hours	27	8.8
4-6 Hours	13	4.2
7-9 Hours	15	4.9
10-12 Hours	1	0.3
More than 12 Hours	8	2.6
Officially work from home during the COVID-19		
1-3 Hours	47	15.3
4-6 Hours	89	29
7-9 Hours	111	36.2
10-12 Hours	46	15
More than 12 Hours	14	4.6

Source: Authors' calculations

Measurement Tools

In the current study, a set of questionnaires was given to the participants. It included the demographic information form, Cognitive Flexibility Inventory (CFI), Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ), Work-Life Balance Scale (WLBS), and The Job Crafting Questionnaire (JCQ).

Demographic Information Form

This form included questions about the demographic characteristics of the participants (i.e., age, gender, education level, occupation, location, number of children, living arrangement, household income, and related work form home in COVID-19 pandemic).

Cognitive Flexibility Inventory (CFI)

The 20-item self-report questionnaire of Cognitive Flexibility Inventory was developed by Dennis & Vander Wal (2010) to measure two cognitive flexibility subscales which were named as alternatives and control. The Cognitive Flexibility Inventory was used to evaluate the ability of individuals to produce alternative, harmonious, appropriate, and balanced thoughts in difficult situations. Alternatives subscale includes 13 items and Control subscale includes 7 items which are rated on a 7-point Likert type scale ranging from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 7 (Strongly agree). The scoring for subscales is calculated by adding up all of these items. The Cronbach's alpha values of the Alternatives subscale were .91 in the first and last measurements, while the Cronbach's alpha values of the Control subscale were .86 in the first measurement and .84 in the last measurement, and .91 for the overall scale (Dennis & Vander Wal, 2010). Items 2, 4, 7, 9, 11 and 17 of the scale are reverse coded.

The Turkish adaptation of Cognitive Flexibility Inventory was conducted by Gülüm and Dağ (2012). The Turkish adaptation of Cognitive Flexibility Inventory is

rated on a 5-point Likert type scale ranging from 1 (Strongly disagree) to 5 (Strongly agree). The Cronbach's alpha values of the Alternatives subscale were .89, while the Cronbach's alpha values of the Control subscale were .85, and .90 for the overall scale (Gülüm & Dağ, 2012). The lowest score that can be obtained from the Alternatives subscale is 13, and the highest score is 65. The lowest score that can be obtained from the Control subscale is 7, and the highest score is 35. Thus, the score that can be obtained from the whole scale is between 20 and 100.

Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ)

The Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) was developed by Gross and John (2003) to assess the levels and the types of emotion regulation of individuals. The ERQ is a 10-item measure of emotion regulation with six items that measure Reappraisal subscale, and four items that measure Suppression subscale. Participants are asked to indicate how accurately each item best described them using a 7-point Likert type scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree) where higher scores indicate higher levels of emotion regulation. The internal consistency was calculated by the Cronbach alpha coefficients by Gross and John (2003: 348). The scale was internally consistent with Cronbach's alphas ranging from .80 to .82 for the reappraisal, and from .73 to .76 for the suppression. Additionally, test-retest reliability in a three month interval was found to be .69 for both tests (Gross & John, 2003).

Turkish adaptation of ERQ was conducted by Eldeleklioğlu and Eroğlu (2015: 1157). In Turkish adaptations of ERQ was used 7-point Likert type scaling. In Eldeleklioğlu and Eroğlu (2015) study, the Cronbach alpha coefficient was found to be .73 for Suppression subscale, and .78 for Reappraisal subscale. In addition, test-retest reliability was found to be .72 for Suppression test, and .74 for Reappraisal test (Eldeleklioğlu & Eroğlu, 2015). The lowest score that can be obtained from the Reappraisal subscale is 6, and the highest score is 42. The lowest score that can be obtained from the Suppression subscale is 4, and the highest score is 28.

Work-Life Balance Scale (WLBS)

WLBS was developed by Netemeyer, Boles, and McMurrian (1996) to assess employees' work-life conflict. It consists of 10-items measured on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Lower scores on this scale indicate higher work-life balance. The Cronbach's alpha values of the Work-to-Life Imbalance subscale were .88, while the Cronbach's alpha values of the Life-to-Work Imbalance subscale were .89.

The scale was adapted to Turkish by Efeoğlu (2006). In Turkish adaptations of WLBS was used 5-point Likert type scaling. The Cronbach's alpha values of the Work to Life Imbalance subscale were .90, while the Cronbach's alpha values of the Life to Work Imbalance subscale were .86, and .86 for the overall scale (Efeoğlu, 2006). The lowest score that can be obtained from each of the Work to Life Imbalance and Life to Work Imbalance subscales is 5, and the highest score is 25. Thus, the score that can be obtained from the whole scale is between 10 and 50. Since scale items and subscales

measure imbalance, all items were reverse coded in this study, and it was aimed to reach balance.

The Job Crafting Questionnaire (JCQ)

The Job Crafting Questionnaire (JCQ) was developed by Slemp & Vella-Brodrick (2013) to assess the levels of job crafting related with individuals' work. The JCQ is a 15-item measure with 5 of them measuring Task Crafting subscale, 5 of them measuring Relational Crafting subscale, and 5 of them measuring Cognitive Crafting subscale. The JCQ is rated on a 6-point Likert type scale ranging from 1 (Hardly ever) to 6 (Very often). Higher scores on the subscales indicate higher levels of job crafting. The Cronbach's alpha values of the Cognitive Crafting subscale were .90, the Cronbach's alpha values of the Task Crafting subscale were .86, the Cronbach's alpha values of the Relational Crafting subscale were .84, and .91 for the overall scale (Slemp & Vella-Brodrick, 2013).

Turkish adaptation of JCQ was conducted by Kerse (2017). The Turkish adaptation of JCQ is rated on a 5-point Likert type scale ranging from 1 to 5, and 19-items. The Cronbach's alpha values of the Cognitive Crafting subscale were .86, the Cronbach's alpha values of the Task Crafting subscale were .76, the Cronbach's alpha values of the Relational Crafting subscale were .84, and .92 for the overall scale (Kerse, 2017). The lowest score that can be obtained from the Task Crafting subscale is 7, and the highest score is 35. The lowest score that can be obtained from the Cognitive Crafting subscale is 5, and the highest score is 25. The lowest score that can be obtained from the Relational Crafting subscale is 7, and the highest score is 35. Thus, the score that can be obtained from the whole scale is between 19 and 95.

Table 2: Descriptive Characteristics of the Study Variables

Variables	N	M	SD
Cognitive Flexibility	307	83.79	9.95
Alternatives	307	56.37	6.07
Control	307	27.42	5.50
Emotion Regulation	307	42.99	7.50
Reappraisal	307	30.34	5.28
Suppression	307	12.66	5.44
Work Life Balance	307	35.78	9.74
Work to Life Imbalance	307	15.80	6.09
Life to Work Imbalance	307	19.98	4.90
Job Crafting	307	79.14	11.43
Task Crafting	307	28.72	4.61
Cognitive Crafting	307	21.61	3.44
Relational Crafting	307	28.82	5.58

Source: Authors' calculations

Data collected by scales was analyzed for descriptive statistics, and frequency distributions. Cronbach alpha was applied to test the reliability of the scales in this study. The scales were observed to exploratory factor analysis to determine validity.

Finally, in line with the aim of the research, AMOS program was used to examine the complex relationships between the variables for measurement and structural models. IBM SPSS 25 and AMOS 25 were used for analysis in this study.

The main characteristics for the scales and their subscales are involved in the analysis. Centralization and variability measures for scales are shown in following Table 2.

Factor Structures of the Measurement Tools and Correlations of Scales

For Cognitive Flexibility, two sub-factors are alternatives and control. CMIN/DF value is 3.042; CFI value is 0.878 for cognitive flexibility inventory; GFI value is 0.857 for cognitive flexibility scale; IFI value is 0.879; RMSEA is 0.082.

For Emotion Regulation, two sub-factors are reappraisal and suppression. CMIN/DF value is 4.062; CFI value is 0.896 for emotion regulation questionnaire; GFI value is 0.915 for emotion regulation questionnaire; IFI value is 0.897; RMSEA is 0.100. However, if the item is deleted because the ER3_reappraisal item factor loading is low, the new values are CMIN/DF value is 2.653; CFI value is 0.954 for emotion regulation questionnaire; GFI value is 0.953 for emotion regulation questionnaire; IFI value is 0.955; RMSEA is 0.074.

For work-life balance, two sub-factors are work-to-life and life-to-work. CMIN/DF can be brought to acceptable level by drawing a covariance between e9 and e10. CMIN/DF value is 3.698; CFI value is 0.967 for work-life balance scale; GFI value is 0.926 for work-life balance scale; IFI value is 0.967; RMSEA is 0.094.

For Job Crafting, three sub-factors are task crafting, cognitive crafting, and relational crafting. CMIN/DF can be brought to acceptable level by drawing a covariance between e18 and e19. CMIN/DF value is 3.075; CFI value is 0.890 for the job crafting questionnaire; GFI value is 0.853 for the job crafting questionnaire; IFI value is 0.891; RMSEA is 0.082.

Pearson correlation analyses were used to investigate the linear associations among the variables of study for participants. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 1: Correlations between all scales and subscales

	CF	CF-AI	CF-Co	ER	ER-Re	ER-Su	WLB	WLB-W	WLB-L	JC	JC-Tc	JC-Cc	JC-Rc
CF	$\alpha=.91$												
CF-AI	.88**	$\alpha=.89$											
CF-Co	.85**	.48**	$\alpha=.89$										
ER	.10	.19**	-.03	$\alpha=.65$									
ER-Re	.43**	.45**	.28**	.69**	$\alpha=.80$								
ER-Su.	-.28**	-.17**	-.31**	.71**	-.02	$\alpha=.82$							
WLB	.37**	.21**	.43**	-.08	.17**	-.28**	$\alpha=.93$						
WLB-W	.29**	.16**	.35**	-.06	.14*	-.22**	.91**	$\alpha=.94$					
WLB-L	.36**	.22**	.42**	-.08	.17**	-.28**	.86**	.57**	$\alpha=.91$				
JC	.53**	.54**	.37**	.15**	.36**	-.14**	.21**	.14*	.25**	$\alpha=.91$			
JC-Tc	.49**	.51**	.33**	.16**	.30**	-.08	.16**	.11*	.17**	.84**	$\alpha=.83$		
JC-Cc	.48**	.47**	.35**	.12*	.31**	-.13*	.25**	.19**	.26**	.81**	.62**	$\alpha=.85$	
JC-Rc	.39**	.40**	.27**	.11	.30**	-.14*	.16**	.08	.21**	.86**	.51**	.53**	$\alpha=.88$

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Notes: CF=Cognitive Flexibility, CF-AI= Alternatives dimension of CF; CF-Co=Control dimension of CF; ER=Emotion Regulation, ER-Re=Reappraisal dimension of ER, ER-Su=Suppression dimension of ER; WLB=Work-Life Balance, WLB-W=Work-to-Life dimension of WLB, WLB-L=Life-to-Work dimension of WLB; JC=Job Crafting, JC-Tc=Task Crafting dimension of JC, JC-Cc=Cognitive Crafting dimension of JC, JC-Rc=Relational Crafting dimension of JC. Cronbach's Alpha values are also shown.

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics and MANOVA Results for Education Level

	High School		Education Level University		Master/Ph.D.		One-way MANOVA		
	<i>m</i>	<i>sd</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>sd</i>	<i>m</i>	<i>sd</i>	<i>F</i>	η^2	<i>p</i>
Alternatives Control	51.25	15.02	56.08	5.93	56.82	5.84	2.01	.013	.135
	26.25	9.36	27.16	5.81	27.73	5.05	.50	.003	.605
Reappraisal	30.75	11.3	30.6	5.12	30.05	5.29	.40	.003	.671
Suppression	19.5	3.11	13.35	5.66	11.74	5.02	6.75	.042	.001
Work to Life	13.25	6.08	15.34	6.3	16.35	5.84	1.41	.009	.246
Life to Work	20.5	4.65	19.6	5.08	20.37	4.72	.96	.006	.384
Task Crafting	23	9.2	28.88	4.6	28.71	4.4	3.22	.021	.041
Cognitive Crafting	19.25	7.32	21.69	3.4	21.59	3.37	.98	.006	.376
Relational Crafting	25	5.83	29.13	5.27	28.59	5.87	1.32	.009	.269

Note 1. Multivariate $F(18, 592) = 1.64, p < .05$; Wilks' $\lambda = .91$, partial $\eta^2 = .05$.

Note 2. The mean scores that do not share same superscript on the same row are significantly different from each other at least at $p < .006$ level.

Source: Authors' calculations

One-Way Manova

Several MANOVAs were used to examine the differences among the levels of demographics in terms of all subscales of all scales (i.e., alternatives, control, reappraisal, suppression, work-to-life, life-to-work, task crafting, cognitive crafting, and relational crafting). Univariate analyses of education level were investigated to see detailed findings, because one-way MANOVA analyses of only education level were appeared to be significant among demographic variables. Bonferroni correction was calculated for 9 dependent variables (all subscales) (.05/9), and new significance level was appeared as .006 (Table 4).

In order to investigate the differences among education levels of participants in terms of all subscales, one-way MANOVA was used, and the result was found as significant [Multivariate $F(18, 592) = 1.64, p < .05$; Wilks' $\lambda = .91$, partial $\eta^2 = .05$]. According to the results of univariate analyses, between high school, university, and master/doctorate were significantly different from each other in terms of suppression [$F(2, 304) = 6.75, p < .006$, partial $\eta^2 = .04$]. Participants with a high school degree ($m = 19.5, sd = 3.11$) had significantly higher suppression scores than participants with a master/doctorate degree ($m = 11.74, sd = 5.02$), and participants with a university degree ($m = 13.35, sd = 5.66$) had significantly higher suppression scores than participants with a master/doctorate degree ($m = 11.74, sd = 5.02$).

Independent-Samples T Test and Paired-Samples T Test Analysis

Relationships between gender and all scales were tested based on independent-samples T Test analysis, there is relationship between gender and emotion regulation (Table 5). The mean of females ($X = 41.99, SD=7.22$), males ($X = 44.35, SD=7.71$) different, and this difference is statistically significant ($t(304)=-2.744, p=0.006, r=0.08$). To calculate the effect size r , first *Cohen's d* was calculated, and then $r = [d^2 / (d^2+4)]^{1/2}$ process was used (Ferguson, 2016). According to these results, emotion regulation level of female is more negative than males. In particular, although there is no significant relationship between gender and reappraisal, the relationship between gender and suppression is significant (Table 6). The mean of females ($X = 11.77, SD=4.96$), males ($X = 13.87, SD=5.85$) different, and this difference is statistically significant ($t(247.729)=-3.291, p=0.001, r=0.09$). According to these results, suppression scores of females is more negative than males. Thus, males tend to suppress their emotions more than females.

Table 3: Independent-Samples T Test Results for Gender and Emotion Regulation

Emotion Regulation	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p
Female	177	41.989	7.22	304	-2.744	.006
Male	129	44.349	7.705			

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 4: Independent-Samples T Test Results for Gender and Suppression

Suppression	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p
Female	177	11.774	4.963	247.729	-3.291	.001
Male	129	13.868	5.855			

Source: Authors' calculations

The mean of remote workers before COVID-19 ($X = 38.48$, $SD=9.3$), those who started remote work with the COVID-19 pandemic ($X = 35.06$, $SD=9.75$) different, and this difference is statistically significant ($t(305)=2.523$, $p=0.012$, $r=0.09$). According to these results, work-life balance level of those who started remote work with the COVID-19 pandemic is more negative than the remote workers before COVID-19.

Table 5: Independent-Samples T Test Results for Remote Workers before COVID-19 and Those who Started Remote Work with the COVID-19 on Work-Life Balance

Work-Life Balance	N	Mean	SD	df	t	p
Those who started remote work with the COVID-19	243	35.062	9.746	305	2.523	.012
Remote workers before COVID-19	64	38.484	9.303			

Source: Authors' calculations

The Model of The Study

In this part of the study, the relationships between all variables of the study are modeled according to the purpose of the research as shown in Figure 1. The covariances of the variables were also checked. Model fit measures structural equation model, according to hypotheses is shown in Table 8.

Figure 1: Path Analysis According to Hypotheses

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 6: Model 1 Fit Measures Path Analysis According to Hypotheses

Model Fit Measures			
Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	60.480		
DF	8		
CMIN/DF	7.560	Between 1 and 3	Terrible
CFI	0.931	> 0.95	Acceptable
SRMR	0.088	< 0.08	Acceptable
RMSEA	0.146	< 0.06	Terrible
PClose	0	> 0.05	Not Estimated

Source: Authors' calculations

However, control, which is the sub-dimension of cognitive flexibility, has a direct effect on the sub-dimensions of work-life balance. Figure 2 was drawn because the variance of these relationships (control→work-to-life, control→life-to-work) are very explanatory. The final version of the model is Figure 2. Model fit measures structural equation model final version is also shown in Table 10.

Table 9: Goodness-of-Fit Indices for Two Models

	χ^2 *	d.f.*	p*	χ^2 /d.f.	GFI*	AGFI*	CFI*	IFI*	RMSEA*
Model 1	60.480	8	.000	7.560	.962	.784	.931	.933	.146
Model 2	10.755	6	.096	1.793	.992	.943	.994	.994	.051

Source: Authors' calculations

The goodness-of-fit indices of the Model 2 are better than the Model 1 in most of the indices (Table 9).

Figure 2: Path Analysis Final Version

***. Coefficient is significant at the 0.001 level; **. Coefficient is significant at the 0.01 level; *. Coefficient is significant at the 0.05 level.

Source: Authors' calculations

Table 70: Model 2 Fit Measures Path Analysis Final Version

Model Fit Measures			
Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	10.755		
DF	6		
CMIN/DF	1.793	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.994	> 0.95	Excellent
SRMR	0.039	< 0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.051	< 0.06	Excellent
PClose	0.425	> 0.05	Excellent

Source: Authors' calculations

As seen in Figure 2, in addition, only the path to Work-to-Life and Life-to-Work variables is drawn from Control. As a result, the new model fit measures are shown in Table 10. The relationships between all variables of the study are modeled according to the purpose of the research as shown in Figure 2. The covariances of the variables were also checked (Table 11).

Table 11: Covariances between Alternatives, Control, Reappraisal, and Suppression

Relationships	Estimate	S.E	C.R	p
Alternatives <--> Control	.175	.023	7.559	***
Reappraisal <--> Suppression	-.027	.068	-.393	.694
Alternatives <--> Reappraisal	.183	.026	7.135	***
Alternatives <--> Suppression	-.110	.037	-2.996	.003
Reappraisal <--> Control	.191	.041	4.676	***
Control <--> Suppression	-.325	.064	-5.106	***

Source: Authors' calculations

As seen in Table 11, there are significant relationships between alternatives and control, alternatives and reappraisal, alternatives and suppression, reappraisal and control, control, and suppression. However, there is no significant relationship between reappraisal and suppression. Reappraisal and suppression are dimensions of Emotion Regulation Questionnaire but stated that a total score cannot be obtained from the scale, and this is because reappraisal and suppression are two different strategies of emotion regulation, are not complementary (Eldeleklioglu & Eroglu, 2015).

Table 12: Path Analysis Between All Dimensions

Paths	Estimate	S.E	C.R	p
Task Crafting <-- Alternatives	.595	.084	7.043	***
Cognitive Crafting <-- Alternatives	.512	.090	5.714	***
Relational Crafting <-- Alternatives	.498	.108	4.601	***
Task Crafting <-- Reappraisal	.060	.041	1.455	.146
Cognitive Crafting <-- Reappraisal	.088	.043	2.025	.043
Relational Crafting <-- Reappraisal	.131	.053	2.496	.013
Task Crafting <-- Control	.099	.048	2.044	.041
Cognitive Crafting <-- Control	.129	.051	2.522	.012
Relational Crafting <-- Control	.066	.062	1.058	.290
Task Crafting <-- Suppression	.017	.025	.702	.483
Cognitive Crafting <-- Suppression	-.012	.026	-.456	.648
Relational Crafting <-- Suppression	-.040	.032	-1.252	.210
Work-to-Life <-- Task Crafting	-.103	.131	-.786	.432
Life-to-Work <-- Task Crafting	-.118	.102	-1.156	.248
Work-to-Life <-- Cognitive Crafting	.247	.128	1.927	.054
Life-to-Work <-- Cognitive Crafting	.191	.100	1.921	.055
Work-to-Life <-- Relational Crafting	-.090	.100	-.893	.372
Life-to-Work <-- Relational Crafting	.100	.078	1.290	.197
Work-to-Life <-- Control	.521	.089	5.832	***
Life-to-Work <-- Control	.469	.069	6.759	***

Pathways between all dimensions are shown in Table 12. First, significant direct effects of cognitive flexibility subscales (alternatives, control) and emotion regulation subscales (reappraisal, suppression) on job crafting subscales (task crafting, cognitive crafting, relational crafting) are examined. The effect of alternatives on task crafting is 0.60; the effect of alternatives on cognitive crafting is 0.51; the effect of alternatives on relational crafting is 0.50; both are significant at $p < 0.001$. The effect of control on task crafting is 0.10, significant at $p = 0.04$; the effect of control on cognitive crafting is 0.13, significant at $p = 0.01$; the effect of control on relational crafting is 0.07, it is not significant. The effect of reappraisal on task crafting is 0.06, it is not significant; the effect of reappraisal on cognitive crafting is 0.09, significant at $p = 0.04$; the effect of reappraisal on relational crafting is 0.13, significant at $p = 0.01$. Suppression has no significant effect on job crafting dimensions.

Secondly, direct effects of job crafting subscales on work-life balance subscales (work-to-life, life-to-work) are examined for the model. Job crafting dimensions have no significant effect on work-life balance dimensions.

Lastly, control has a direct and significant effect on work-life balance sub-dimensions. The effect of control on work-to-life is 0.52, and the effect of control on life-to-work is 0.47, both are significant at $p < 0.001$.

5. Discussion

Theoretical models reveal three important relationship categories for the research data. First, alternatives have a significant effect on task crafting, cognitive crafting, and relational crafting. Second, control has a significant effect on task crafting, cognitive crafting, work-to-life balance, and life-to-work balance. Third, reappraisal has a significant effect on cognitive crafting and relational crafting. The paths consist of cognitive flexibility dimensions (alternatives, control) and emotion regulation dimensions (reappraisal, suppression) as independent variable, job crafting dimensions (task crafting, cognitive crafting, relational crafting) as mediating variable, and work-life balance dimensions (work-to-life, life-to-work) as dependent variable. The findings will be discussed in detail in the following section.

Cognitive Flexibility – Emotion Regulation

Emotion regulation and cognitive flexibility are highly related terms. Alternatives and control as cognitive flexibility dimensions and reappraisal and suppression as emotion regulation dimensions are dealt with in the study. The first finding is the relationship between alternatives and reappraisal, and this is in line with the cognitive-behavioral approach literature (e.g. McRae et al., 2012). Kalia

and Knauff (2020) stated that there is a high degree of correlation between reappraisal and alternatives. However, some studies did not find a relationship between reappraisal and alternatives (e. g. Guassi Moreira et al., 2020). Reappraisal reduces the behavioral and experiential outcomes of unwanted emotions and is often used in negative emotions (Gross & John, 2003). Although searching for alternatives is sometimes costly in terms of time, it provides an advantage in reaching positive thoughts in communication or daily events (Hommel & Colzato, 2017). Both are effective strategies to improve the quality of life. In the cognitive-behavioral approach, thoughts are the antecedents of emotions, and replacing thoughts with positive ones will ensure that emotions are re-evaluated (Blacker et al., 2008: 129). Because of this relationship in the cognitive-behavioral approach, it was thought that a positive relationship would be observed between reappraisal and alternatives in this study, and this hypothesis was supported. Another significant relationship was found between alternatives and suppression. Due to their structure, alternatives and suppression are thought to act in the opposite direction. While alternatives involve the process of changing thoughts, suppression is the suppression of the emotion as it is without being changed. Suppression can lead to low self-esteem in the long term, and studies have shown that suppression is associated with increased psychopathology (Cameron & Overall, 2018; Aldao et al., 2010). In contrast, alternatives have an important place in the treatment of psychological disorders such as depression (Hollon & Dimidjian, 2014). Looking at the output of this relationship, it was assumed that there would be a negative relationship between alternatives and suppression, and this hypothesis was also supported.

Secondly, a correlation was found between control and reappraisal. Considering the reappraisal strategy in cognitive flexibility and emotion regulation, the use of reappraisal increases in situations that require control (Haines et al., 2016). Thanks to control, re-evaluation strategies that emerge with self-discipline and effort are used to achieve the positive (Savickas & Porfeli, 2012). In this way, as mentioned in Lahad's (1997) coping model, it is of great importance to ensure controllability and the expression of emotions and the evaluation of alternative questions. In this respect, it has been considered that control is an important dimension of cognitive flexibility as much as alternatives, and in this study, it was thought that there might be a positive relationship between control and reappraisal. The hypothesis is supported by the results. Another result is the inverse relationship between control and suppression. Considering that control leads to positive results such as reappraisal and alternatives cognitively, it is known that the use of suppression will create negative consequences for individuals in the long-term. Therefore, as suppression increases, the controllability of situations decreases (Sexton & Dugas, 2008). In this study, it was assumed that control and suppression were negatively related, and that control would decrease as suppression increased. According to the results, this hypothesis was also supported.

Third, the reappraisal processing mechanism is similar to alternatives in cognitive flexibility (e.g. Malooly et al., 2013). Alternatives and reappraisal are not

the same thing, but they are known to have a meaningful relationship. In this study, a significant relationship was found between alternatives and reappraisal. In addition, it was thought that there was a negative relationship between alternatives and suppression, and this relationship was supported by the results. Considering the relationship between alternatives and reappraisal and the positive results between them, it was thought that there might be a negative relationship between reappraisal and suppression. In addition, Balzarotti et al. (2010), the negative relationship between suppression and ventilation of emotion, and the positive relationship between reappraisal and positive reinterpretation, suggested that there may be a negative relationship between reappraisal and suppression. But this hypothesis was rejected. Because no significant relationship was found between reappraisal and suppression. Eldeleklioğlu and Eroğlu (2015) stated that a total score cannot be obtained from the Emotion Regulation Questionnaire. Reappraisal and suppression scores are collected separately, and separate evaluations are made about the reappraisal strategy and suppression strategy. Thus, it is not possible to evaluate the individual's emotion regulation with this scale. This may be the reason why no relationship was found between reappraisal and suppression in this study. In the studies, these two subscales were handled independently, and their relationships were not reported (e.g. Cabello et al., 2013; Balzarotti et al., 2010; Eldeleklioğlu & Eroğlu, 2015). In contrast, Spaapen et al. (2014: 46) found that there is a negative significant relationship between reappraisal and suppression. On the other hand, the original version of the Emotion Regulation Questionnaire (ERQ) consists of 10 items. This 10-item scale confirmed the measurement invariance in the study conducted with students from Italy and Germany (Sala et al., 2012). However, in this study, the ER3_reappraisal item was deleted because it provided better model fit. Similarly, in the measurement invariance study (Spaapen et al., 2014) conducted with non-students in the United Kingdom and Australia, the 10-item ERQ was stated to be unsustainable. By removing one item, it was stated that the measurement invariance of the ERQ-9 was provided for both countries. As in this study, Spaapen et al. (2014), the item that should be removed was ER3_reappraisal. Although it needs to be supported by more studies, it has been seen that the sample of Turkey, Australia, and United Kingdom is similar in this respect.

Cognitive Flexibility and Job Crafting

After the covariance relations, the path analysis results will now be discussed. Firstly, alternatives have an impact on all dimensions of job crafting. The highest impact of Alternatives is on task crafting. Next, it has an effect on cognitive crafting. It also has a positive and significant effect on relational crafting, which is another job crafting dimension. All dimensions of job crafting are positive for individuals, and as the score of each sub-dimension increases, job crafting also increases. Looking at the literature, although there are not many studies examining the relationship between cognitive flexibility and job crafting, according to Amabile et al. (2005), behaviors such as problem-solving and idea generation increase thanks to seeing alternatives, thus contributing to job crafting with easier creativity. Producing alternatives enables multidimensional thinking instead of a fixed point

of view while task crafting and enables overqualified individuals to better reveal their talents (Debus et al., 2020). Also, being able to see alternatives is a cognitive process, and facilitates cognitive crafting (e.g. Riasnugrahani et al., 2019). Supervisors may recommend that their employees change some aspects of their work temporarily or permanently by seeing alternatives (Duffy et al., 2018), which will be related to cognitive crafting. On the other hand, being able to see alternatives through flexibility positively affects job crafting, including relational crafting (Loi et al., 2019). In this study, the effect of alternatives on task crafting, cognitive crafting, and relational crafting was observed, and the hypotheses were supported.

Secondly, it was found that the control dimension of cognitive flexibility influenced the task crafting dimension of job crafting. In addition, the control variable was also found to influence cognitive crafting. Flexibility enables one to cope with controllable situations and makes difficult tasks perceived as controllable (Koeske et al., 1993), and thus it will be easier to perform task crafting. The control variable is a sub-dimension of cognitive flexibility, and as control increases, cognitive flexibility score also increases. In other words, cognitive processes should be used for the controllable perception of an event (e.g. Miyake et al., 2000). In this direction, individuals who cognitively craft their work achieve this by having more control over their work and being able to make active changes in their work (Petrou et al., 2018). In this study, hypotheses were supported thanks to the positive effect of control on task crafting and cognitive crafting. On the other hand, since the controllable perception of conflicts or difficulties in a relationship seems advantageous for resolution and mediation, it is thought that control will influence relational crafting. Resolving conflicts in relationships through mediation is effective in high activation of the nucleus accumbent, which is the reward center in the brain (Rafi et al., 2020). On the other hand, there may be a negative relationship between control and relational crafting, and the reason may be that control in relationships is perceived negatively in some cases. Although perceiving situations as controllable is not exactly the same as controlling a romantic relationship, the fact that colleagues in the workplace feel control over their relationships can reduce intimacy and lead to a decrease in trust (e.g. Stets, 1995). However, although it was thought that control would influence relational crafting, no significant effect was found, and this hypothesis was rejected. As mentioned before, there are not enough studies examining the relationship between job crafting and cognitive flexibility, so the lack of a relationship between control and relational crafting cannot be explained in a healthy way.

Emotion Regulation and Job Crafting

Thirdly, reappraisal influences cognitive crafting. In addition, the effect of reappraisal on relational crafting was also observed. The effect of emotion regulation should not be ignored in crises such as COVID-19 (Restubog et al., 2020). Emotional experiences have an important place in changing the perception of job role, especially in job crafting processes (Lichtenthaler & Fischbach, 2018). Considering that reappraisal acts similarly to the alternative's mechanism, the effect

of alternatives on job crafting dimensions suggests that reappraisal may also influence job crafting dimensions. Reappraisal uses cognitive processes because it is necessary to review an event due to its structure. It is important for business to make different evaluations while doing cognitive crafting. A positive reappraisal, in other words, reducing a negative attitude requires cognitive effort and is beneficial for relationships (e.g. Penley et al., 2002). In addition, psychological distress can be reduced thanks to the reappraisal relationship with cognitive crafting (Sakuraya et al., 2016), and thus the negativities in relationships can be re-evaluated. For example, individuals may reappraisal positively by thinking they are busy instead of thinking badly about their relationship when their coworkers don't answer the phone. In this study, hypotheses were supported similarly with this information. On the other hand, it is thought that reappraisal may also influence task crafting. Because, as Lichtenthaler and Fischbach (2018) stated, emotional experiences are important in processes in the workplace. In addition, it is known that as age increases, emotional experiences increase, and commitment increases (Rowden, 2000). However, because more youth were involved in this study, reappraisal, a dimension of emotion regulation, may not have a significant effect on task crafting. In the sample of this study, an emotional process may not have emerged yet in tasks at work. Thus, the hypothesis that reappraisal would influence task crafting was rejected.

Job Crafting and Work-Life Balance

Next, the effect of job crafting sub-dimensions on work-life balance sub-dimensions is not significant. When the literature is examined, there are studies that have a positive effect of job crafting on work-life balance. For example, Sturges (2012) stated that work-life balance can be improved through job crafting practices. In addition, studies have shown that job crafting has a positive effect on well-being (e.g. Tims et al., 2013), and work-life balance will increase when well-being increases (e.g. Fouché & Martindale, 2011). Slowiak and DeLongchamp's (2021) study has indeed shown that job crafting has an impact on work-life balance in addition to work engagement and burnout. Based on these data in the literature, it is thought that all dimensions of job crafting will have an impact on all dimensions of work-life balance. However, looking at the results, the hypothesis was rejected. Akkermans and Tims (2017) thought that there would be a negative relationship between job crafting and work-home interference, but a positive relationship was found between job crafting and work-home interference. In the model drawn in Figure 1, it was seen that cognitive crafting had an effect on work-life balance, but in the latest version, Figure 2, the direct effect of control on work-life balance also eliminated the effect of job crafting dimensions on work-life balance.

Control and Work-Life Balance

Finally, control in cognitive flexibility has a direct effect on work-life balance dimensions. The effect of control on work-to-life is greater than the effect of control on life-to-work. In the hypotheses and the first model (Figure 1), it was

not predicted that the control variable would have a highly explanatory variance on work-life balance. However, it has been seen that the sample of this study can directly increase their work-life balance by perceiving the events as controllable. In the study, it was predicted that the use of reappraisal in cognitive flexibility and emotion regulation would positively affect job crafting, and the work-life balance of remote workers would improve by improving tasks, cognitive processes, and relationships thanks to increased job crafting. In the cognitive behavioral approach, it is known that thoughts affect emotions, and emotions reveal behavior (see e.g. Beck, 2005). It was thought that one of the behaviors that emerged in this study would be job crafting. It was expected that the reward of the behavior would be an increase in work-life balance. Therefore, the hypotheses were formed as in Figure 1.

The COVID-19 pandemic is a time of crisis. The world has faced consequences that it has never encountered before. The rise of working from home is one of the biggest examples of this (e.g. ILO, 2020). It is important to keep individuals' perceptions of control alive in crisis and disaster situations. For example, within the scope of psychological first aid, to increase the control of an affected individual, he or she may be asked where his phone is, and whether he has a relative with whom he would like to report his situation. Increased controllable states in individuals are important for recovery (Antonovsky, 1979). It seems that in this study, the participants achieved their work-life balance by focusing on the things they could control.

On the other hand, when low job control and low work-life balance are combined, job demands seem to create more stress (Chiang et al., 2010). In addition, it was observed that work-life balance and locus of control affect career adjustment together, and the positive effect of the two variables was observed (Zhou et al., 2016). Individuals' locus of control may also be related to work-life balance. Because, in COVID-19, individuals may have shown COVID-19 as the reason for the tasks they could not complete, or they were internally focused on what they could achieve. The protection of individuals in COVID-19 has been realized by wearing masks, keeping distance, and maintaining hygiene. Similarly, individuals perceived situations as controllable while working at home and were able to balance the time they should devote to work and the time they should devote to their private lives. Or, on the contrary, they may have overlooked the controllable aspects of the situation and reduced their work-life balance.

6. Conclusions

Studying the proposed model during the COVID-19 pandemic is important because of the way that work-life interaction has changed during this period. The key findings of the study can be summed up by three primary findings when the data collected from the participants is assessed. First, it was determined that alternatives and control in cognitive flexibility and reappraisal in emotion

regulation had a favorable impact on job crafting. Second, there is no meaningful connection between suppressing and job crafting, even though it is believed to have a negative impact on it. It was also supported that job crafting has a positive effect on work-life balance.

This study is the first to incorporate all four of these factors. It provides a distinctive viewpoint and contribution in this way. While environmental effects are at the forefront in work-life balance studies related to human psychology, individual cognitive and emotional processes are at the forefront in this study. The present study will be an original resource for those who want to work with these variables again. No matter what period we are in, no matter how we work, we will always try to maintain the balance of work-life balance. Individuals can achieve this more easily thanks to cognitive flexibility and reappraisal.

Cognitive flexibility, emotion regulation, and job crafting strategies will be beneficial for work-life balance, not only in companies but in all organizational environments. Organizations can enable their employees to learn these strategies. It should be known that especially cognitive flexibility and reappraisal are closely related to cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). CBT application has an easy and time-saving structure. It is possible to increase the well-being of employees with CBT applications in the workplace.

The collection of the data of the study from a single source created a limitation. In addition, the fact that it is a cross-sectional study is another limitation, since the way individuals perceive situations may differ over time. On the other hand, the fact that the 3rd question in the Emotion Regulation Questionnaire is perceived as a suppression strategy rather than a reappraisal strategy in the sample of this study is also a limitation related to scale. The study was conducted with a limited sample, and age and education distributions were not equally distributed in each group. The data collection method was done online only due to the pandemic, and it is impossible to know that the participants were of the same interest in answering all the questions. In future studies, the number of samples can be increased and an equal number of people from all education levels and age groups can be reached.

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